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SBA-15/hydrotalcite nanocomposite as an efficient support for the immobilization of heteropolyacid: A triply-hybrid catalyst for the synthesis of 2-amino-4H-pyrans in water

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Sadjadi, S.², Zadsirjan, V.¹., Farzaneh, V.³

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran

² Gas Conversion Department, Faculty of Petrochemicals, Iran Polymer and Petrochemical Institute, Vanak, Tehran, Iran

³ Iran Polymer and Petrochemical Institute, Iran

Abstract

To circumvent the high solubility and low surface area of heteropolyacid and in attempt to develop a bi-functional heterogeneous catalyst for promoting organic transformations, heteropolyacid was embedded in functionalized SBA-15 and subsequently hybridized with layered double hydroxide. The catalyst could be considered as a bi-functional catalyst with both acidic and basic properties. The acidic properties emerged from the SBA-15 and heteropolyacid component while layered double hydroxide render the catalyst basic. The catalyst was characterized by using SEM/EDX, FT-IR, XRD, ICP-AES, BET and elemental mapping analysis. The catalytic activity of the catalyst was studied for promoting one-pot three-component condensation of aromatic aldehydes, malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate and C-H activated acidic molecules in aqueous media for the synthesis of 2-amino-4H-pyran derivatives. The catalyst exhibited high catalytic activity, which was superior to the previously reported ones. Moreover, the reusability of the catalyst was excellent and the leaching of heteropolyacid was dramatically suppressed. High yields, short reaction times, eco-friendly conditions, simplicity of the procedure, reusability of the catalyst and broad substrate scope are the merits of this protocol.

Keyword: 2-Amino-4H-pyrans, Heteropolyacid, SBA, Hydrotalcite, Multi-component reactions